

Warped Frames: dispersive vs. non-dispersive sampling

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ABSTRACT

Conventional Time-Frequency and Time-Scale Representations are often too rigid to capture fine details of sound or musical signals. Adaptation of ideal time-frequency tilings is often desirable in order to represent the signal in terms of components that are meaningful from a physical or perceptual point of view.

Remapping of the time and frequency axes by means of time and frequency warping can help achieve the desired flexibility of the representation. However, in the general case, the conjugate variable is affected as well, so that the resulting representation plane is distorted. In this paper we show methods to redress the conjugate distortion introduced by warping, both in the unsampled case of the integral Short-Time Fourier Transform and in the sampled case of generalized Gabor frames.

Ultimately, the methods illustrated in this paper allow for the construction and computation of Gabor-like non-uniform time frequency representations in which the new frames are obtained from uniform Gabor frames by frequency warping both the time variable and the time index. This provides a very general design procedure based on a prescribed warping map that can be derived, e.g., from a tonal scale.

1. INTRODUCTION

Time-frequency representations play a central role in the analysis, synthesis, coding and processing of sound signals. In this context, the most commonly used representation is the phase vocoder or Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), which has uniform time and frequency resolutions. However, non-uniform resolution is desirable in several applications. For example, the analysis and synthesis frequency bands can be adapted to a perceptual scale, achieving clear advantages in synthesis and coding due to the direct psycho-acoustic relevance of each component. In synthesis-by-analysis schemes, the frequency bands can be adapted to characteristics of the signal suggested, for example, by the frequencies of the partials of the tones,

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Figure 1. Frequency warping uniform frequency bands according to a 1/3 of octave scale (top); resulting frequency band characteristics (bottom). Here b is the frequency shift in Hz of the original uniform bands.

which in many instruments, such as the piano in the low register or percussions, are not harmonically related.

Non-uniform frequency bands can always be thought of as obtained from uniform bands through a frequency map, i.e. a monotonically increasing function remapping the frequency axis. In certain cases, e.g. critical bands, the frequency map is given by experimentally fitted curves. In other cases, such as in the vibration of stiff strings or bars, the frequency map is derived from a wave dispersion characteristic. Sometimes the map is only specified at a finite number of points; a continuous curve can be obtained by interpolation. The application of a frequency map is known in filter design as frequency warping, a practice dating back to Constantinides's spectral transformations [1]. Frequency warping applied to a uniform system of bands is shown in Fig. 1 for adaptation to an equally tempered scale.

In a similar way, non-uniform analysis time intervals can be prescribed by remapping the time axis of the signal before performing uniform time-frequency analysis. The uniform analysis of the time warped signal achieves non-uniform time resolution and can be employed, e.g., to in-

crease the time resolution close to signal transients and to reduce the time resolution in stationary portions of the signal.

However, frequency warping is not a time-shift invariant operation: it actually disrupts the time organization of signals. Uniform time-frequency analysis of the frequency warped signal results in a frequency dependent distortion of the time axis in the warped time-frequency representation. Similarly, the time warped time-frequency representation shows time dependent distortion of the frequency axis. Thus, warping one variable prior to uniform time-frequency analysis affects the conjugate variable in the representation plane.

In this paper, we address the problem of eliminating or mitigating the distortion of the conjugate variable in warped representations. We focus on the integral Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) and on its sampled version of Gabor frames. The method is quite general and can be applied to other representations such as time-scale.

Based on recently developed results [2–4], we address the problem of building perfect reconstruction structures for the time-frequency representation of signals that allow for arbitrary selection of bands specified according to a frequency map. Mathematically this amounts to constructing flexible frames that allow for parametric selection of the frequency bands of their atoms.

Just as Gabor frames can be obtained by uniformly sampling the integral STFT, the warped frames can be obtained as a result of nonuniform sampling in time-frequency. Nonuniform sampling theorems based on a time warping map were introduced in [5] and their adaptation to frequency sampling is immediate. Applications of frequency warping to time-frequency analysis date back to [6]. However, work previous to our paper did not take dispersion into account, which blurs the results of the analysis.

Orthogonal wavelets and wavelet frames [7], especially in their complex form [8], can be thought of as an example of nonuniform sampling of the time-frequency plane where the sampling grid is the time-scale grid $\{ma^n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}, m \in \mathbb{Z}}$. Further adaptation leading to more flexible time-frequency resolution settings were introduced in [9, 10] for frequency and in [11] for time. The methods found in this paper do not make any assumption on the sampling grid. Rather, the grid is derived from the warping map, which can be assigned arbitrarily within smooth and one-to-one functions.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we review the concept of applying time and frequency warping to time-frequency representations derived from the continuous time Short-Time Fourier Transform, pointing out the problems introduced by dispersion. In Section 3 we illustrate how dispersion can be counteracted by means of further warping operations in the time-frequency domain. In Section 4 we attempt to apply the same redressing methods to frames, which allow for sampled time-frequency analysis and synthesis, and we provide the conditions by which the redressing of dispersion is exact. In Section 5 we illustrate the redressing method for frames, providing design examples and applications to audio signals. In Section 6 we draw our conclusions.

2. WARPED TIME-FREQUENCY

A uniform time-frequency representation is obtained by applying the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) operator \mathcal{S} to the signal s :

$$[\mathcal{S}s](\tau, \nu) = \langle s, h_{\tau, \nu} \rangle = \langle s, \mathbf{T}_\tau \mathbf{M}_\nu h_{0,0} \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} s(t) \overline{h_{0,0}(t - \tau)} e^{-j2\pi\nu(t - \tau)} dt, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{T}_\tau s(t) = s(t - \tau)$ is the time-shift operator, $\mathbf{M}_\nu s(t) = e^{j2\pi\nu t} s(t)$ is the modulation operator and the overbar denotes complex conjugation. The operator \mathcal{S} acts over time signals and the angular frequency ν is considered as a parameter. In (1), the analysis windows

$$h_{\tau, \nu}(t) = [\mathbf{T}_\tau \mathbf{M}_\nu h_{0,0}](t) = h_{0,0}(t - \tau) e^{j2\pi\nu(t - \tau)} \quad (2)$$

are modulated and shifted versions of a unique time window $h_{0,0}$. Their Fourier transforms are related to the Fourier transform of the original window $\hat{h}_{0,0}$ as follows:

$$\hat{h}_{\tau, \nu}(f) = \hat{h}_{0,0}(f - \nu) e^{-j2\pi f \tau}. \quad (3)$$

Since $[\mathcal{S}s](\tau, \nu) = s(\tau) * \overline{h_{0, \nu}(-\tau)}$, where the symbol $*$ denotes convolution, one can rewrite (1) in the frequency domain w.r.t. τ as follows:

$$[\widehat{\mathcal{S}s}](f, \nu) = \overline{\hat{h}_{0, \nu}(f)} \hat{s}(f) = \overline{\hat{h}_{0,0}(f - \nu)} \hat{s}(f). \quad (4)$$

Non-uniform time-frequency representations can be obtained from uniform ones via time and / or frequency warping, as discussed in Section 2.2, after we formally introduce warping operators in the next section.

2.1 Warping Operators

A 1D warping operator performs a remapping of the abscissae, as obtained through function composition. A time warping operator \mathbf{W}_γ is completely characterized by a function composition operator in the time domain:

$$s_{tw} = \mathbf{W}_\gamma s = s \circ \gamma, \quad (5)$$

where γ is the time warping map and s_{tw} is the time-warped signal. Similarly, a frequency warping operator \mathbf{W}_θ is completely characterized by a function composition operator \mathbf{W}_θ in the frequency domain:

$$\hat{s}_{fw} = \widehat{\mathbf{W}_\theta s} = \widehat{\mathbf{W}_\theta} \hat{s} = \mathbf{W}_\theta \hat{s} = \hat{s} \circ \theta, \quad (6)$$

where θ is the frequency warping map, which transforms the Fourier transform $\hat{s} = \mathcal{F}s$ of a signal s into the Fourier transform $\hat{s}_{fw} = \mathcal{F}s_{fw}$ of another signal s_{fw} , where \mathcal{F} is the Fourier transform operator and the hat over a symbol denotes the Fourier transformed quantity (signal or operator). We affix the \sim symbol over the map θ as a reminder that the map operates in the frequency domain. Accordingly, we have $\mathbf{W}_\theta = \mathcal{F}^{-1} \widehat{\mathbf{W}_\theta} \mathcal{F} = \mathcal{F}^{-1} \mathbf{W}_\theta \mathcal{F}$.

If the warping map is one-to-one and almost everywhere differentiable then a unitary form of the warping operator can be defined by amplitude scaling, as given by the

square root of the derivative of the map (dilation function). For example, a unitary frequency warping operator $\mathbf{U}_{\tilde{\theta}}$ has frequency domain action

$$\hat{s}_{fw}(\nu) = \left[\widehat{\mathbf{U}_{\tilde{\theta}} s} \right] (\nu) = \sqrt{\left| \frac{d\theta}{d\nu} \right|} \hat{s}(\theta(\nu)), \quad (7)$$

where ν is angular frequency. We assume henceforth that all warping maps are almost everywhere increasing so that the magnitude sign can be dropped from the derivative under the square root.

Unitary frequency warping ensures that the original signal energy is preserved. While bands are stretched or shrunk, the amplitudes are correspondingly reduced or increased so that the areas under the magnitude square Fourier transform in the warped bands are the same as the areas under the magnitude square Fourier transform of the original signal in the original bands.

Frequency warping generally disrupts the time organization of signals. Indeed, the time-shift operator \mathbf{T}_{τ} does not commute with the frequency warping operator:

$$\left[\widehat{\mathbf{W}_{\tilde{\theta}} \mathbf{T}_{\tau} s} \right] (\nu) = \left[\widehat{\mathbf{W}_{\theta} \mathbf{T}_{\tau} s} \right] (\nu) = e^{-j2\pi\theta(\nu)\tau} \hat{s}(\theta(\nu)), \quad (8)$$

which is different from $\left[\widehat{\mathbf{T}_{\tau} \mathbf{W}_{\tilde{\theta}} s} \right] (\nu) = e^{-j2\pi\nu\tau} \hat{s}(\theta(\nu))$, unless the map θ is the identity map. Thus, an event that starts at time T in the original signal, is dispersed into events starting at times $\phi_d(\nu)T$, where $\phi_d(\nu) = \theta(\nu)/\nu$ is the phase delay of the warping map, which depends on frequency unless the map is linear. This time dispersion results in audible de-synchronization of the signal and, as we will see, also in a distorted warped time-frequency representation. Similarly, time warping disrupts the frequency organization of signals resulting in time dependent frequency dispersion.

2.2 Warped Time-Frequency Representations

Remapping signals prior to STFT allows for a reinterpretation of the representation elements: while the organization of the representation (tiling) remains the same, the elements capture different components of the signal. Time warping dilates / shrinks and displaces the characteristic analysis time intervals (resolution and centers) w.r.t. signals. Frequency warping remaps the characteristic analysis frequency bands w.r.t. signals (bandwidths and centers).

Given a (time or frequency) warping operator \mathbf{W}_{γ} , the warped STFT is defined through the operator \mathcal{S}_{γ} as follows

$$\begin{aligned} [\mathcal{S}_{\gamma} s] (\tau, \nu) &= [\mathcal{S} \mathbf{W}_{\gamma} s] (\tau, \nu) = \\ \langle \mathbf{W}_{\gamma} s, h_{\tau, \nu} \rangle &= \langle s, \mathbf{W}_{\gamma}^{\dagger} h_{\tau, \nu} \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

which is indeed a warped version of (1), where $\mathbf{W}_{\gamma}^{\dagger}$ is the adjoint of the warping operator. If the warping operator is unitary then we have $\mathbf{W}_{\gamma}^{\dagger} = \mathbf{W}_{\gamma}^{-1} = \mathbf{W}_{\gamma^{-1}}$. In that case, warping the signal prior to STFT is perfectly equivalent to perform STFT analysis with inversely warped windows. The warped STFT is unitarily equivalent to the STFT so that a number of properties concerning conditioning and reconstruction hold [12].

If \mathbf{W}_{γ} is a unitary time warping operator, the warped STFT analysis elements are

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{h}_{\tau, \nu}(t) &= [\mathbf{W}_{\gamma^{-1}} h_{\tau, \nu}] (t) = \\ \sqrt{\frac{d\gamma^{-1}}{dt}} \hat{h}_{0,0}(\gamma^{-1}(t) - \tau) &e^{j2\pi\nu(\gamma^{-1}(t) - \tau)}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

These elements are formed by time warped windows centered at times $t = \gamma(\tau)$, as desired. However, the analysis frequencies are time-dependent. In fact, the instantaneous frequencies of the elements in (10), which are given by the time derivative of the phase of the complex exponential, are $\nu \frac{d\gamma^{-1}}{dt}$.

Similarly, if $\mathbf{W}_{\tilde{\theta}}$ is a unitary frequency warping operator, the Fourier transforms of the warped STFT analysis elements are

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{h}_{\tau, \nu}(f) &= [\widehat{\mathbf{W}_{\tilde{\theta}^{-1}} h_{\tau, \nu}}] (f) = \\ \sqrt{\frac{d\theta^{-1}}{df}} \hat{h}_{0,0}(\theta^{-1}(f) - \nu) &e^{-j2\pi\theta^{-1}(f)\tau}, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

which shows how the analysis elements are obtained from frequency warped modulated windows centered at frequencies $f = \theta(\nu)$. The windows are time-shifted with dispersive delay, where the group delay is $\tau \frac{d\theta^{-1}}{df}$.

In the applications we would like to produce spectrograms with non-uniform time or frequency resolution but the dispersion introduced by warping results in misalignment and spreading of the time-frequency components in the conjugate variable of the warped one. In the next section we will show how further warping in the time-frequency plane can redress the warped representations.

3. REDRESSING THE WARPED STFT

To address the problem of realigning the frequency warped STFT $[\mathcal{S}_{\tilde{\theta}} s] (\tau, \nu)$, consider its Fourier transform w.r.t. the time variable τ . This can be written in the form (4) by replacing the Fourier transform of the signal with that of the frequency warped signal:

$$\left[\widehat{\mathcal{S} \mathbf{W}_{\tilde{\theta}} s} \right] (f, \nu) = \overline{\hat{h}_{0,0}(f - \nu)} \sqrt{\frac{d\theta}{df}} \hat{s}(\theta(f)). \quad (12)$$

Recall that f is the angular frequency variable conjugate to time τ in the time-frequency plane. Performing unitary frequency warping on this variable by means of the inverse frequency map θ^{-1} one obtains:

$$\left[\widehat{\mathbf{W}_{\tilde{\theta}^{-1}} \mathcal{S} \mathbf{W}_{\tilde{\theta}} s} \right] (f, \nu) = \overline{\hat{h}_{0,0}(\theta^{-1}(f) - \nu)} \hat{s}(f), \quad (13)$$

where we have used the fact that

$$1 = \frac{d[\theta(\theta^{-1}(f))]}{df} = \frac{d\theta}{d\alpha} \Big|_{\alpha=\theta^{-1}(f)} \frac{d\theta^{-1}}{df}. \quad (14)$$

The redressed frequency warped STFT (13) is again in the form of a time-invariant filtering operation (convolution in time domain) where the filters are frequency warped versions of the modulated windows in (4). As a result, the dispersive delays in the analysis elements (11) are brought

back to non-dispersive delays, the Fourier transform of the redressed analysis elements being

$$\hat{h}_{\tau,\nu}(f) = \left[\mathbf{T}_{\tau} \widehat{\mathbf{W}_{\tilde{\theta}} h_{0,\nu}} \right] (f) = \hat{h}_{0,0}(\theta^{-1}(f) - \nu) e^{-j2\pi f \tau}. \quad (15)$$

It is possible to interpret (13) as the similarity transformation $\mathbf{W}_{\tilde{\theta}}^{\dagger} \mathcal{S} \mathbf{W}_{\tilde{\theta}}$ on the STFT operator, which is time-shift covariant.

A similar procedure for realigning the time-warped STFT can be derived by considering the inverse Fourier transform w.r.t. angular frequency in the time-frequency plane (second argument of the STFT) and by applying inverse time warping to the time variable conjugated to frequency in time-frequency. To simplify the result, the inverse Fourier transform can be taken with respect to time origin τ . This leads to a conjugate time covariant version of the time warped STFT in which frequency dispersion is eliminated.

4. WARPED GABOR FRAMES

4.1 Gabor frames

Given a window function h and two sampling parameters $a, b > 0$, the set of functions

$$\mathcal{G}(h, a, b) = \{ \mathbf{T}_{na} \mathbf{M}_{mb} h : q, n \in \mathbb{Z} \} \quad (16)$$

is called a *Gabor system*. A signal s can be projected over a Gabor system by taking the scalar products $\langle s, \mathbf{T}_{na} \mathbf{M}_{mb} h \rangle$. These are exactly evaluations of the STFT of a signal with window h at the time-frequency grid of points (na, qb) . Here we have defined the Gabor system using the same convention as in the definition (1) of the STFT. Usually, Gabor systems are defined with a reverse order of time-shift and frequency modulation operators, i.e. $\{ \mathbf{M}_{mb} \mathbf{T}_{na} h : q, n \in \mathbb{Z} \}$. However, the extra phase factors that are introduced to convert from one definition to the other are perfectly irrelevant when establishing properties of the system. Even in the computation the extra phase factors cancel out in the analysis-synthesis algorithm, so they can be ignored.

A sequence of functions $\{ \psi_l \}_{l \in I}$ in the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} is called a frame if there exist both positive constant lower and upper bounds A and B , respectively, such that

$$A \|s\|^2 \leq \sum_{l \in I} |\langle s, \psi_l \rangle|^2 \leq B \|s\|^2 \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{H}, \quad (17)$$

where $\|s\|^2 = \langle s, s \rangle$ is the norm square or total energy of the signal. Frames generate signal expansions, i.e., the signal can be perfectly reconstructed from its projections over the frame.

A Gabor system that is a frame is called a *Gabor frame*. In this case, the signal can be reconstructed from the corresponding samples of the STFT. While not unique, reconstruction can be achieved with the help of a dual frame, which in turn is a Gabor frame generated by a dual window \tilde{h} . Perfect reconstruction depends on the choice of the window and the sampling grid. One can show that there exist no Gabor frames when $ab > 1$.

4.2 Warping Gabor frames

From (17) it is easy to see that any unitary operation on a frame results in a new frame with the same frame bounds A and B [12]. In particular, unitary operators can be applied to Gabor frames to obtain new frames. Depending on the operator, the resulting frames are not necessarily of the Gabor type, as the atoms are not generated by shifting and modulating a single window function.

Conceptually, starting from a Gabor frame (analysis) $\{ \varphi_{n,q} \}_{q,n \in \mathbb{Z}}$ and dual frame (synthesis) $\{ \gamma_{n,q} \}_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{n,q} &= \mathbf{T}_{na} \mathbf{M}_{qb} h \\ \gamma_{n,q} &= \mathbf{T}_{na} \mathbf{M}_{qb} g, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where h and g are dual windows, warped frames can be generated by unitarily warping the signal s prior to analysis and unitarily unwarping it after the synthesis:

$$\begin{aligned} s &= \mathbf{U}_{\tilde{\theta}}^{\dagger} \sum_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}} \langle \mathbf{U}_{\tilde{\theta}} s, \varphi_{n,q} \rangle \gamma_{n,q} = \\ &\sum_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}} \langle s, \mathbf{U}_{\tilde{\theta}}^{\dagger} \varphi_{n,q} \rangle \mathbf{U}_{\tilde{\theta}}^{\dagger} \gamma_{n,q}, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{U}_{\tilde{\theta}}$ is a unitary frequency warping operator. Defining the frequency warped frame (analysis) $\{ \tilde{\varphi}_{n,q} \}_{q,n \in \mathbb{Z}}$ and dual frame (synthesis) $\{ \tilde{\gamma}_{n,q} \}_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\varphi}_{n,q} &= \mathbf{U}_{\tilde{\theta}}^{\dagger} \varphi_{n,q} = \mathbf{U}_{\tilde{\theta}^{-1}} \mathbf{T}_{na} \mathbf{M}_{qb} h \\ \tilde{\gamma}_{n,q} &= \mathbf{U}_{\tilde{\theta}}^{\dagger} \gamma_{n,q} = \mathbf{U}_{\tilde{\theta}^{-1}} \mathbf{T}_{na} \mathbf{M}_{qb} g, \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

one obtains the signal expansion

$$s = \sum_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}} \langle s, \tilde{\varphi}_{n,q} \rangle \tilde{\gamma}_{n,q}. \quad (21)$$

However, warped Gabor frames suffer from the same problem as the warped STFT: as a result of frequency warping, the time organization of the analysis and synthesis systems is disrupted; the windows are time-shifted with frequency dependent shifts. Indeed the Fourier transforms of the warped Gabor frame elements are

$$\hat{\tilde{\varphi}}_{n,q}(f) = \sqrt{\frac{d\theta^{-1}}{df}} \hat{h}(\theta^{-1}(f) - qb) e^{-j2\pi\theta^{-1}(f)na}, \quad (22)$$

which bear frequency dispersive delays. In other words dispersive time samples are produced by the direct application of the warped frame analysis. Similar problems are encountered when time-warping Gabor frames.

The magnitude Fourier transforms $\hat{h}(\theta^{-1}(f) - qb)$ of a set of frequency warped modulated windows corresponding to $1/3$ octave frequency resolution is shown in Fig. 1, together with a scaled version $\frac{1}{b}\theta^{-1}$ of the warping map, which maps warped frequency to fractional band number, i.e., the integer values of $\frac{1}{b}\theta^{-1}$ correspond to the center frequencies of the bands.

In the next section we are applying a similar procedure to the one we introduced in the warped STFT in order to realign the time-frequency samples.

4.3 Redressing Warped Gabor Frames

The evaluation of the warped Gabor expansion coefficients

$$\tilde{c}_{n,q} = \langle s, \tilde{\varphi}_{n,q} \rangle \quad (23)$$

is identical to that of a time-frequency sampled warped STFT. In order to redress the frequency warped STFT into a time covariant representation we have introduced additional inverse frequency warping with respect to the time variable τ in the time-frequency plane. However, in the warped Gabor frames (20) this variable is sampled at instants na . Therefore, in order to parallel our warped STFT redressing procedure in the warped Gabor frames, one can only apply a discrete-time form of frequency warping to the time index n .

It is possible to show [13, 14] that if the discrete-time frequency warping map ϑ is one-to-one and onto $[-\frac{1}{2}, +\frac{1}{2}]$, and almost everywhere differentiable there, then the set of sequences

$$\eta_m(n) = \int_{-\frac{1}{2}}^{+\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{d\vartheta}{d\nu}} e^{j2\pi(n\nu - m\vartheta(\nu))} d\nu, \quad (24)$$

where $n, m \in \mathbb{Z}$, forms an orthonormal basis of $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z})$. These are recognized as generalized Laguerre sequences [9, 10, 15], which are the inverse discrete-time Fourier transforms of warped harmonic complex sinusoids in the frequency domain interval $[-\frac{1}{2}, +\frac{1}{2}]$. The map ϑ can be extended over the entire real axis as congruent modulo 1 to a 1-periodic function.

Given a sequence $\{x(n)\}$ in $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z})$, the scalar products

$$\tilde{x}(m) = \langle x, \eta_m \rangle_{\ell^2(\mathbb{Z})} \quad (25)$$

generate another sequence $\{\tilde{x}(m)\}$ in $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z})$, which satisfies

$$\hat{\tilde{x}}(\nu) = \sqrt{\frac{d\vartheta^{-1}}{d\nu}} \hat{x}(\vartheta^{-1}(\nu)), \quad (26)$$

where the $\hat{\cdot}$ symbol, when applied to sequences, denotes discrete-time Fourier transform. Thus, $\overline{\eta_m(n)}$ defines the nucleus of an inverse unitary frequency warping $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z})$ operator $\mathbf{D}_{\tilde{\vartheta}^{-1}} = \mathbf{D}_{\tilde{\vartheta}}^\dagger$. Clearly, the transposed conjugate sequences $\mu_m(n) = \eta_m(m)$ form the nucleus of a unitary frequency warping $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z})$ operator $\mathbf{D}_{\tilde{\vartheta}}$.

In order to limit or eliminate time dispersion in the frequency warped Gabor expansion, one can apply the discrete-time frequency warping operator $\mathbf{D}_{\tilde{\vartheta}^{-1}}$ to the time sequence of expansion coefficients over the warped Gabor frame (23), i.e., with respect to index n . Since the operator is applied only on the time index, for generality, one can include dependency of the map and of the sequences η_n on the frequency index q , which will be useful in the sequel. The new coefficients are obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\tilde{c}}_{n,q} &= \left[\mathbf{D}_{\tilde{\vartheta}_q^{-1}} \tilde{c}_{\bullet,q} \right] (n) = \sum_{m \in \mathbb{Z}} \overline{\eta_{n,q}(m)} \langle s, \tilde{\varphi}_{m,q} \rangle = \\ &= \left\langle s, \sum_{m \in \mathbb{Z}} \eta_{n,q}(m) \tilde{\varphi}_{m,q} \right\rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

In order to reconstruct the signal from the coefficients $\tilde{\tilde{c}}_{n,q}$ one can first recover the coefficients $\tilde{c}_{n,q}$, which stems from the completeness and orthogonality of the set $\{\eta_{n,q}\}_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}$, and then combine them with the dual warped frame elements:

$$s = \sum_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}} \tilde{c}_{n,q} \tilde{\gamma}_{n,q} = \sum_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}} \sum_{m \in \mathbb{Z}} \tilde{\tilde{c}}_{m,q} \eta_{m,q}(n) \tilde{\gamma}_{n,q}. \quad (28)$$

Hence, defining the redressed frequency warped Gabor analysis and synthesis frames as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\tilde{\varphi}}_{n,q} &= \mathbf{D}_{\tilde{\vartheta}_q^{-1}} \tilde{\varphi}_{\bullet,q} = \sum_m \eta_{m,q}(m) \tilde{\varphi}_{m,q} \\ \tilde{\tilde{\gamma}}_{n,q} &= \mathbf{D}_{\tilde{\vartheta}_q^{-1}} \tilde{\gamma}_{\bullet,q} = \sum_m \eta_{n,q}(m) \tilde{\gamma}_{m,q}, \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

from (27) and (28) we have:

$$s = \sum_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}} \tilde{\tilde{c}}_{n,q} \tilde{\tilde{\gamma}}_{n,q} = \sum_{n,q \in \mathbb{Z}} \langle s, \tilde{\tilde{\varphi}}_{n,q} \rangle \tilde{\tilde{\gamma}}_{n,q}. \quad (30)$$

Indeed, the redressing discrete-time warping transformation is based on an orthonormal and complete expansion in $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z})$, which leads to the unitary equivalence of the redressed warped frames with the warped frames.

In order to verify the extent of our redressing method, we compute the Fourier transforms of the redressed frame. Exploiting the periodicity of the discrete-time redressing frequency warping map one can show that:

$$\hat{\tilde{\tilde{\varphi}}}_{n,q}(f) = A(f) \hat{h}(\theta^{-1}(f) - qb) e^{-j2\pi n \vartheta_q(a\theta^{-1}(f))}, \quad (31)$$

where

$$A(f) = \sqrt{\frac{d\theta^{-1}}{df}} \sqrt{\frac{d\vartheta_q}{d\nu}} \Big|_{\nu=a\theta^{-1}(f)}. \quad (32)$$

Hence, the effect of the dispersive delays would be counteracted if

$$\vartheta_q(a\theta^{-1}(f)) = d_q f \quad (33)$$

for any $f \in \mathbb{R}$, where d_q are positive constants controlling the time scale in each frequency band. In this case, the Fourier transforms of the redressed frame elements simply become:

$$\hat{\tilde{\tilde{\varphi}}}_{n,q}(f) = \sqrt{\frac{d_q}{a}} \hat{h}(\theta^{-1}(f) - qb) e^{-j2\pi n d_q f}. \quad (34)$$

Furthermore, if all d_q are identical, all the time samples would be aligned to a uniform time scale throughout frequencies.

However, each map ϑ_q is constrained to be congruent modulo 1 to a 1-periodic function, while the global warping map θ can be arbitrarily selected. Furthermore, having to be one-to-one in each unit interval, the functions ϑ_q can at most experience an increment of 1 there.

In the general case, a perfect time realignment of the components is not guaranteed. However, locally, within the essential bandwidths of the warped modulated windows it is possible to linearize the phase of the complex exponentials in (31).

We remark that, by construction, the redressed warped Gabor systems are guaranteed to be frames for any choice of the maps ϑ_q satisfying the stated periodicity conditions, even when the phase is not completely linearized.

5. EXAMPLES AND APPLICATIONS

The redressing method is a powerful technique to generate exact time-frequency representations adapted to non-uniform grids using arbitrary warping maps. In this section we illustrate two examples based on non-uniform frequency resolution adapted to a tempered scale. In the first case, the chosen windows have compact support in the frequency domain. In the second case, the windows are compactly supported in the time domain. The methods applies, however, also to windows that are not compactly supported in either domain.

In both our examples we define the redressed analysis and synthesis frames as in (29) and try to enforce condition (33). Actually, since we start with tight Gabor frames [16], analysis and synthesis frames coincide.

5.1 The Painless Case

In the so called “painless” case, where the window h is chosen to have compact support in the frequency domain, one can exactly eliminate the dispersive delays with the help of (29). In fact, to fix our ideas, suppose that the bandwidth of the window h is Kb , with K a positive integer, i.e., $\hat{h}(f) = 0$ for $|f| \geq Kb/2$. This corresponds to an overlap-add scheme in the frequency domain [4] – for example, the choice $K = 2$ corresponds to the case of half window length overlap in the frequency domain (see Fig. 1) – which allows one to satisfy the frame condition (17) even tightly ($A = B = 1$) with a simple choice of the window [4]. In particular, one could use the frequency domain cosine window:

$$\hat{h}(\nu) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{2a}{K}} \cos \frac{\pi\nu}{\beta} & \text{if } -\frac{\beta}{2} \leq \nu < +\frac{\beta}{2} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

where $\beta > 0$ is the total bandwidth of the window and $K > 1$ is an integer, a is the time sampling interval and we let $b = \beta/K$. In that case the warped modulated windows $\hat{h}(\theta^{-1}(f) - qb)$ will be nonzero only for $\theta((q - K/2)b) < f < \theta((q + K/2)b)$.

In the painless case, condition (33) only needs to be satisfied by the map ϑ_q in this interval. Equivalently, we require

$$\vartheta_q(a\nu) = d_q\theta(\nu), \quad (q - \frac{K}{2})b < \nu < (q + \frac{K}{2})b, \quad (36)$$

which is possible if on one hand the variation of the argument of the map ϑ_q in (36) satisfies

$$a[(q + \frac{K}{2})b - (q - \frac{K}{2})b] = Kab \leq 1 \quad (37)$$

and, on the other hand, if also the variation of the map ϑ_q over the warped modulated window bandwidth satisfies

$$d_q[\theta((q + \frac{K}{2})b) - \theta((q - \frac{K}{2})b)] = d_q B_q \leq 1, \quad (38)$$

where $B_q = \theta((q + \frac{K}{2})b) - \theta((q - \frac{K}{2})b)$ is the full bandwidth of the warped modulated window. The first of these conditions only requires $ab \leq 1/K$, which does not depend on q and can be satisfied assigning sufficient redundancy (oversampling) of the initial Gabor frame. Incidentally, this is the same condition for the original Gabor system to form a frame. A valid choice is $K = 2$, which

Figure 2. Locally eliminating dispersion by means of discrete-time frequency warping. Black line: curve derived from the original map θ by amplitude scaling. Gray line: discrete-time frequency warping characteristics for local delay linearization.

requires $ab \leq 1/2$. For the second condition, one needs to select $d_q \leq 1/B_q$, as intuitively clear from the sampling theorem. If there is an upper bound B to the bandwidths B_q then one can choose identical $d_q = 1/B$, $q \in \mathbb{Z}$, to satisfy the sampling condition with uniform rates.

An example of local linearization of the phase is shown in Fig. 2, plotted in the abscissa $\nu = \theta^{-1}(f)$, where the black curve is the amplitude scaled warping map $d_q\theta(\nu)$ and the gray curve represents the map $\vartheta_q(a\nu)$, which is $1/a$ -periodic. Amplitude scaling the warping map θ allows the values of the map to lie in the range of the discrete-time warping map ϑ_q . The amplitude scaling factors are the new time sampling intervals d_q of the redressed warped Gabor expansion.

The choice of the initial sampling interval a allows all the maps $\{\vartheta_q\}_{q \in \mathbb{Z}}$ to be arbitrarily specifiable to match $d_q\theta(\nu)$ in the intervals where the Fourier transforms of the warped modulated windows (warped frame elements) are nonzero. Therefore, the warping map design method to eliminate dispersive sampling in the frequency warped Gabor elements is consistent when the elements are compactly supported in the frequency domain.

The score and the analysis of a singing phrase using a redressed warped Gabor frame adapted to the 12-tone scale are reported in Fig. 3. It is easy to see that the score of the singing part can be easily extracted from the non-uniform spectrogram.

5.2 Redressing in the Painful Case

In the painless case, the obtained redressed warped Gabor frame elements are identical in form to the ones generated in [4] by means of an ad-hoc procedure, where aliasing is canceled in the frequency domain. However, the redressing method by means of (29) for the warped frames presented in this paper can be applied to any frame.

For example, one can start from windows that are compactly supported in the time domain, where aliasing is canceled in the time-domain through overlap-add, such as the

Figure 3. Nonuniform 12-tone scale spectrogram of the singing phrase represented in the score line [from *Tom's Diner*, Suzanne Vega], in which it is possible to track in tempered time-frequency scale the score and even the glissando introduced by the singer.

time-domain cosine window. This window is given by

$$h(t) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{2b}{R}} \cos \frac{\pi t}{T} & \text{if } -\frac{T}{2} \leq t < +\frac{T}{2} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (39)$$

where T is the total duration of the window, $R > 1$ is an integer, b is the frequency sampling interval and we let the time shift parameter $a = T/R$.

The Fourier transform of the cosine window, given by

$$\hat{h}(\nu) = \sqrt{\frac{b}{2R}} (\text{sinc}(\nu T - \frac{1}{2}) + \text{sinc}(\nu T + \frac{1}{2})), \quad (40)$$

is plotted in Fig. 4, from which one can see that the main lobe has bandwidth $3/T = 3/Ra$. Assuming this as the essential bandwidth in which to linearize the phase, in order to satisfy (33) here, one needs to select $R \geq 3$, which is the analogon of (37), and $d_q B_q \leq 1$, which is the analogon of (38), where now $B_q = \theta(qb + \frac{3}{2T}) - \theta(qb - \frac{3}{2T})$.

Concurrently, the parameter T can be selected according to the smallest required essential bandwidth. For example, in the case of a tempered scale warping map, in order to have sufficient frequency resolution one can select $\frac{3}{2T} = f_0$, where f_0 is the frequency of the smallest tone to be represented, so that adjacent tones fall away from the main frequency lobe of the window, which gives $a = \frac{3}{2Rf_0}$.

The frequency shift parameter b must be chosen so that $ab \leq 1/R$ for the original Gabor system to be a frame. For $R = 3$ and the chosen value of a , this gives $b \leq 2f_0/3$. However, in practice one would like the tones of the scale to be adequately represented by the warped bands; in our examples we chose $b = f_0/3$.

A zoom of the analysis of the same phrase as in Fig. 3 by means of a redressed warped Gabor frame generated by a

Figure 4. Magnitude Fourier transform of the cosine window.

cosine shaped time domain window is shown in Fig. 5. In spite of the fact that the phase is linearized only in the support of the main lobes of the warped windows, the quality of the result is not appreciably different from that obtained in the painless case. Moreover, perfect reconstruction is still guaranteed.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have introduced a new method to design time-frequency representations with arbitrary non-uniform time or frequency resolutions, based on frequency and time warping. The problems arising from the dispersive sampling introduced by warping are solved by introducing a further warping operation in time-frequency.

The procedure was first applied to the unsampled Short-Time Fourier Transform and, with further constraints, to Gabor frames. In the latter, perfect elimination of dispersion is only possible in particular cases, e.g., when the Gabor frame elements have compact support in the frequency domain (for frequency warping) or in the time domain (for time warping).

The design extends the methods presented in [4] by making use of warping maps to generate a full class of suitable frames with assignable non-uniform time and frequency resolutions and with non-dispersive sampling. It also paves the way to approximations in which the effect of dispersion is minimized within the essential bandwidths of the frame elements when these are not selected, possibly for real time computational needs, to have compact support in the frequency domain.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] A. Constantinides, "Spectral transformations for digital filters," *Proceedings of the Institution of Electrical Engineers*, vol. 117, no. 8, pp. 1585–1590, 1970.

Figure 5. Zoom of the nonuniform 12-tone scale spectrogram of the same singing phrase as in Fig. 3 using a redressed warped Gabor frame generated by a cosine window in the time domain.

- [2] G. A. Velasco, N. Holighaus, M. Dörfler, and T. Grill, “Constructing an invertible constant-Q transform with non-stationary Gabor frames,” in *Proceedings of the Digital Audio Effects Conference (DAFx-11)*, Paris, France, 2011, pp. 93–99.
- [3] P. Balazs, M. Dörfler, F. Jaillet, N. Holighaus, and G. A. Velasco, “Theory, implementation and applications of nonstationary Gabor Frames,” *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 236, no. 6, pp. 1481–1496, 2011.
- [4] G. Evangelista, M. Dörfler, and E. Matusiak, “Phase vocoders with arbitrary frequency band selection,” in *Proceedings of the 9th Sound and Music Computing Conference*, Copenhagen, Denmark, 2012, pp. 442–449.
- [5] J. Clark, M. Palmer, and P. Lawrence, “A transformation method for the reconstruction of functions from nonuniformly spaced samples,” *Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 1151–1165, 1985.
- [6] C. Braccini and A. Oppenheim, “Unequal bandwidth spectral analysis using digital frequency warping,” *IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, vol. 22, pp. 236–244, 1974.
- [7] I. Daubechies, *Ten lectures on wavelets*, ser. CBMS-NSF Regional Conference Series in Applied Mathematics. Philadelphia, PA: Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics (SIAM), 1992, vol. 61.
- [8] N. Kingsbury, “Complex Wavelets for Shift Invariant Analysis and Filtering of Signals,” *Applied and Computational Harmonic Analysis*, vol. 10, pp. 234–253, 2001.
- [9] G. Evangelista, “Dyadic Warped Wavelets,” *Advances in Imaging and Electron Physics*, vol. 117, pp. 73–171, Apr. 2001.
- [10] G. Evangelista and S. Cavaliere, “Frequency Warped Filter Banks and Wavelet Transform: A Discrete-Time Approach Via Laguerre Expansions,” *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 46, no. 10, pp. 2638–2650, Oct. 1998.
- [11] S. Azizi, D. Cochran, and J. McDonald, “Reproducing kernel structure and sampling on time-warped spaces with application to warped wavelets,” *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 789–790, 2002.
- [12] R. G. Baraniuk and D. L. Jones, “Unitary equivalence : A new twist on signal processing,” *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 43, no. 10, pp. 2269–2282, Oct. 1995.
- [13] P. W. Broome, “Discrete orthonormal sequences,” *J. ACM*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 151–168, Apr. 1965. [Online]. Available: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/321264.321265>
- [14] L. Knockaert, “On Orthonormal Muntz-Laguerre Filters,” *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 790–793, apr 2001.
- [15] G. Evangelista and S. Cavaliere, “Discrete Frequency Warped Wavelets: Theory and Applications,” *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 874–885, Apr. 1998, special issue on Theory and Applications of Filter Banks and Wavelets.
- [16] S. Mallat, *A Wavelet Tour of Signal Processing*. Academic Press London, 1998.